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Medical knowledge management and managing knowledge within the health setting

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Abstract

The importance of knowledge has been emphasized as early as the time of Aristotle. However, the term KM is relatively new. KM has become a distinct discipline of science during the mid-1990s with established training courses. The application of KM in Medicine has been recently suggested.

The need to manage knowledge seems obvious, and discussions of intellectual capital have proliferated, but few organizations have acted on that understanding. However, a growing number are doing so. Implementations of "knowledge management" may range from technology-driven methods of accessing, controlling, and delivering information to massive efforts to change corporate culture. Opinions about the paths, methods, and even the objectives of knowledge management abound. Some efforts focus on enhancing creativity — creating new knowledge value — while other programs emphasize leveraging existing knowledge. KM as a discipline that can be incorporated in the medical learning branches includes training and courses taught in the fields of administration, information systems, management, and library, information sciences, computer science, and public health. KM is no longer a passing fad because of the increasing amount of research in this field. The WHO has recently established the Global WHO Knowledge Management team which aims to bridge the know-do gap in global health by fostering an environment that encourages the creation, sharing, and effective application of knowledge to improve health. The aim of this paper is to briefly review the aspects of KM relevant to doctors.

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Knowledge

In practice, the terms information and knowledge are often used interchangeably by writers. However, Davenport and Prusak definition seems to be more logic and accurate. Davenport and Prusak define knowledge as a fluid mix of framed experience, values (principles and standards), contextual information, and expert insight that provides a framework for evaluating and incorporating new experiences and information (Davenport Tom and Prusak lary, 1998) [1]. In

organizations, knowledge often becomes embedded in documents, repositories, and organizational routines, practices, and norms. In their seminal work on knowledge creation, Nonaka and coworkers propose a theory of organizational knowledge creation based on a never ending spiral of tacit and explicit knowledge conversion through socialization, externalization, combination, and internalization (Nonaka Ikujiro 1991), (Nonaka Ikujiro,1996) [2,3]. While explicit knowledge is often precise and can be formally articulated in organizations, tacit knowledge is the know how within individuals that is much harder to express, except through experience (Bohn Roger, 1994) [4]. Supporting this latter point is also the notion that the act of knowing is a social construct of translation and making sense of one's information, experiences, and insights within a given context (Blackerler Frank 1995), Weick Karl (1995) [5, 6].

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Understanding knowledge existence is important for understanding the concept of KM. Knowledge exists in the form of tacit knowledge and explicit knowledge. Tacit knowledge represents internalized knowledge that an individual may not be consciously aware of how he or she accomplishes particular tasks. Explicit knowledge represents knowledge that the individual holds consciously in mental focus, in a form that can easily be communicated to others.

Research suggested that a successful KM effort needs to convert internalized tacit knowledge into explicit knowledge in order to share it. Subsequent research into KM suggested that a distinction between tacit knowledge and explicit knowledge represented an oversimplification and that the notion of explicit knowledge is self-contradictory. Specifically, for knowledge to be made explicit, it must be translated into information (i.e., symbols outside of our heads)

Knowledge exists as an embedded knowledge of a system outside of a human individual (e.g., an information system may have knowledge embedded into its design) and embodied knowledge representing a learned capability of a human body's nervous and endocrine systems.

Knowledge can be exploratory creation of "new knowledge" (i.e., innovation) or represent transfer or exploitation of "established knowledge" within a group, organization, or community. Collaborative environments such as communities of practice or the use of social computing tools can be used for both knowledge creation and transfer.

Knowledge may be accessed at three stages: before, during, or after KM-related activities. Different organizations have tried various knowledge capture incentives, including making content submission mandatory and incorporating rewards into performance measurement plans. Considerable controversy exists over whether incentives work or not in this field and no consensus has emerged. One strategy to KM involves actively managing knowledge. In such an instance, individuals strive to explicitly encode their knowledge into a shared knowledge repository, such as a database, as well as retrieving knowledge they need that other individuals have provided to the repository. Strategy to KM involves individuals making knowledge requests of experts associated with a particular subject on an ad hoc basis. In such an instance, expert individual(s) can provide their insights to the particular person or people needing this.

Knowledge management

Recognition of the growing importance of organizational knowledge was accompanied by concern over how to deal with exponential increases in the amount of available knowledge and increasingly complex products and processes. The computer technology that contributed so heavily to superabundance of information started to become part of the solution, in a variety of domains.

Knowledge management methods are drawn from other disciplines and approaches including systematic literature review, evidence-based decision making, organizational sense making, group and relational development, knowledge creation, information system evaluation, and reflective practitioners. These methods are grouped according to whether they deal with new or existing knowledge sources, or by the individuals involved.

Knowledge management is hard to define precisely and simply. From the views and definitions of several authors KM can be defined as the set of processes that comprises a range of practices used in an organization to identify, create, represent, distribute and enable adoption of insights and experiences. Such insights and experiences comprise knowledge, either embodied in individuals or embedded in organizational processes or practice. Therefore, knowledge management should be a natural function of human organizations. In practice, knowledge management often encompasses identifying and mapping intellectual assets within the organization, generating new knowledge (experiences and information) for competitive advantage within the organization, making vast amounts of the organization information accessible, sharing of best practices, and technology. However, knowledge management was probably first established as discipline and a specific branch of learning in 1995. The immediate purpose of KM is not to improve either worker effectiveness (though it may well do that) or an organization's bottom line. Its purpose is to enhance knowledge processing [7].

KM Technologies and projects

Early KM technologies included online corporate yellow pages as expertise locators and document management systems. Combined with the early development of collaborative technologies (in particular Lotus Notes), KM technologies expanded in the mid-1990s. Subsequent KM efforts leveraged semantic technologies for search and retrieval and the development of e-learning tools for communities of practice

Development of social computing tools (such as blogs and wikis) have allowed more unstructured, self-governing or ecosystem approaches to the transfer,

capture and creation of knowledge, including the development of new forms of communities, networks, or matrixes organizations. However such tools for the most part are still based on text and code, and thus represent explicit knowledge transfer. These tools face challenges in distilling meaningful re-usable knowledge and ensuring that their content is transmissible through diverse channels

The four common types of KM projects noted are to build knowledge repositories, improve knowledge access and use, enhance knowledge environment, and manage knowledge as an asset. Current KM research issues include refining a knowledge vocabulary, taking into account its organizational and cultural contexts, identifying ways of managing and measuring knowledge acquisition, refinement, and use, and nurturing knowledge creation through communities of practice as part of organizational learning [8-11].

Table (1): Motivations leading organizations to undertake a KM

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Making available increased knowledge content in the development and provision of products and services.
Facilitating and managing innovation and organizational learning
Leveraging the knowledge of people across organization
Increasing network connectivity between internal and external individuals
Allowing employees to obtain relevant insights and ideas appropriate to their work
Solving intractable or wicked problems
Managing intellectual capital and intellectual assets in the workforce (such as the expertise and know-how possessed by key individuals).

MEDICAL KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT

Medical KM is a set of principles, tools and practices that enable people to create medical knowledge, and to share, translate and apply what they know to create value and improve effectiveness. The "applied" nature of medical sciences distinguishes it from theoretical sciences. Medical knowledge is complex and doubles in amount every 20 years [12, 13].

Once knowledge has been captured in some form such as a guideline, it can be managed in three related ways [14]:

1. Providing access to the knowledge in paper or electronic libraries [15], Web sites etc. so that doctors and others can find what they need rapidly and interpret it without error;
2. Disseminating knowledge that is of high quality and relevant to decision makers in newsletters, emails, printed educational material [16], verbal presentations [17] etc.
3. Using the knowledge as the substrate for "clinical innovation" methods such as reminders, audit and feedback, decision support systems [18] and other approaches such as outreach visits [19] to bring about changes in clinical practice.

KM as a discipline that can be incorporated in the medical learning branches includes training and courses taught in the fields of administration, information systems, management, and library, information sciences, computer science, public health. KM is no longer a passing fad because of the increasing amount of research in this field.

From a practical standpoint, organizations need to know what, how, why, where, and when to use their knowledge in order to be successful. They also need to view knowledge management (KM) as a strategic way of integrating the organizational know how, processes, and learning.

[20, 21, 22].

Figure-1 shows the main concept and objectives of KM.

Figure (1): The main concept and objectives of KM

The notions of KM have recently been suggested to be established in the health setting. Emphasis has been made on the relevance of KM for the understanding of professional knowledge such as nursing, or on technical representation of expert knowledge in medicine [23, 24]. The 2002 Knowledge Roundtable in health, held at Queen's University in Canada, reported successful examples of KM practices in health settings that include critical care pathways, care planning, evidence-based decision making, and virtual health networks [25]. The roundtable also identified unresolved challenges such as the need for user participation, information technology (IT) investment, and organizational

structures and cultures that support KM. These findings led us to believe that an opportunity exists to apply business KM concepts to create a healthcare delivery system that is strategic, proactive, and knowledge intensive.

Figure-2 shows the overlap between the objectives of KM and Organizational Learning.

Figure-2: The overlap between the objectives of KM and Organizational Learning.

Medical knowledge can be defined as information combined with experience, context, interpretation, and reflection. The knowledge source may be explicit or tacit depending on where it is located (for example, policy document versus individual expert). KM, then, is the systematic approach to translating between the explicit and tacit forms of this knowledge in a given context. Manipulating knowledge as discrete objects, and recognizing that the act of “knowing” is a socially constructed sense-making endeavor requires ongoing dialogue, coordination, and collaboration among policymakers, practitioners, and researchers to be effective and sustainable.

The three medical knowledge sources of particular interest are policy synthesis, research findings, and local practices, referred to by the Canadian Health Services Research Foundation as policy, evidence, and experience, respectively [26].

The core concepts within this framework are knowledge production, use, and refinement, situated within a complex and evolving social context. As such, these concepts are interrelated, iterative,

dynamic, and layered with multiple meanings and interpretations.

Medical editing: A tool and practice of medical KM

Medical editing represents one of the important tools and practices of medical KM enable doctors to create knowledge, and to share, translate and apply what they know to create value and improve effectiveness. Figure-3 shows the practice of medical editing as a tool of medical KM.

Medical editing plays an integral role in the modern production of medical knowledge as it provides the necessary organization of the medical of knowledge into evidence and organized experience. Medical knowledge is created through collection of local experience around specific clinical cases and health services/ programs, generation of new understandings of relationships between specific factors, processes, and outcomes from primary research and policy development such as a

randomized trial or case study in a particular health setting.

, synthesis of available research findings, policy advice, and local experiences in specific areas of health through a critical review process such as systematic review , and identification of individuals, groups, and organizations as resources with

expertise or experience in specific areas of health who are willing to share their tacit knowledge .

A

B

Figure (3) A and B: The practice of medical editing as a tool of medical KM

and effective application of knowledge to improve health.

Currently the Iraqi Ministry of Health KM system consists of:

WHO and the KM

The WHO has recently established the Global WHO Knowledge Management team. Many of the solutions to health problems exist, but are not applied. This is called the "know-do" gap - the gap between what is known and what is done in practice. WHO Knowledge Management team aims to bridge the know-do gap in global health by fostering an environment that encourages the creation, sharing,

1-Section on Knowledge Management-Training and Development Center

2-The Library

3-The New Iraqi Journal of Medicine: The official peer-reviewed medical journal of the Iraqi Ministry of Health

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